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Population Dynamics Of Tilapia (*Oreochromis niloticus*) From River Gongola In Malleri Gombe State, Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

Oreochromis niloticus are the predominant fish species in the Malleri area of River Gongola. However, the fishery has been experiencing a gradual decline over time. There is a lack of recent data on the population dynamics and exploitation pattern of these species, which are essential for sustainable management. Accordingly, the aim of the study was to ascertain the population dynamics of Tilapia (*Oreochromis niloticus*) in Malleri Gombe State Nigeria. Fish samples were obtained from local small-boat fishermen of malleri water body. A total of 852 samples were analyzed with the FiSAT II program (FAO-ICLARM Stock Assessment Tools) to estimate population parameters. The study observed fish lengths ranging from 4.5cm to 51cm. Fish weights varied between 1.61g to 733g. While fish morphometric such as length and weight were measured using standard measuring tape and electronic weighing balance (TH-1000). Length weight relationships were determined using the length and weight frequency data as an input. Length frequency data (LFD) as input on FiSAT 11 software were used to analyze growth parameters such as asymptotic length (L_{∞}), growth coefficient (K) and a growth performance index (ϕ'). Recruitment pulses were analyzed employing "recruitment" option. "Length Converted Catch Curve" option of the said FiSAT 11 was applied to determined mortality indices (which are M^{-yr} , F^{-yr} , and Z^{-yr}) of the fish species. The probabilities of capture at various lengths were $L_{25\%} = 4.00$ cm, $L_{50\%} = 5.50$ cm, and $L_{75\%} = 7.00$ cm. Instantaneous mortality rates were calculated as $M = 0.37$ year⁻¹ for natural mortality, $F = 0.60$ year⁻¹ for fishing mortality, and $Z = 0.97$ year⁻¹ for total mortality. The highest score of 3.73 potential longevity (T_{max}) studied revealed that the species had 1.2 years. Mortality parameters inferred total mortality (Z) was 3.38. Natural mortality fall within 2.21 to 2.29 and fishing mortality were in the range of 1.09 to 1.475. Exploitation ratio (E) revealed that 0.284% of the species were optimally exploited ($E < 0.05$). The malleri water body is rich diverse living aquatic resources which is facing challenges of structural collapse unless management strategies are fully adopted. The host community should be made integral component of aquatic resources management team. And other means of livelihood should be made attractive to reduce pressure on aquatic resources.

Key words: population dynamics, Tilapia (*Oreochromis niloticus*), Malleri water body Gombe State Nigeria.

INTRODUCTION

Fish resources provide humans with affordable, high-quality animal protein. They also generate employment opportunities for a significant portion of the rural population and act as a source of raw materials for a wide range of industrial and recreational applications. (Wake and Geleto, 2019).

Freshwater ecosystems, which are essential to life as we know it on Earth, are the most vulnerable ecosystems worldwide (Gebremedhin; 2021) Fish resources have seen a range of changes in stock diversity and abundance despite their many benefits and vast species diversity due to structural changes in habitat, food composition, and unrestrained exploitation (Nazeef, and Yerima, 2023).

Malleri region of the River Gongola is a crucial breeding and feeding ground for a variety of fish species because of its distinct hydrological patterns and various fish species (Adayi,, 2019), However, anthropogenic stresses including overfishing, habitat degradation, and climate variability are posing an increasing danger to the sustainability of the fish populations in this area (Gordon *et al.*, 2018). Therefore, it is essential to comprehend the population dynamics of fish species in this area in order to create conservation and management plans that work (Gebremedhin, 2021)

Fisheries sustainability, biodiversity preservation, and the sustaining of ecosystems and human livelihoods are all dependent on fish population dynamics, which include growth, recruitment, mortality, and interactions with the environment (Gebremedhin, 2021)

Fish growth refers to the progressive increase in an individual fish's size, including its length, weight, and overall mass, over time. Unlike most animals, fish experience continuous growth throughout their lifespan, a trait known as indeterminate growth (Ahti *et al.*; 2020) the growth of fish is affected by a range of factors, including biological, genetic, and environmental influences (Abd El-Hack *et al.*; 2022)

Fish typically continue to grow throughout their lives, though their growth rate slows considerably once they reach adulthood and old age (Gatto, *et al.*; 2019) Fish can grow at different rates depending on their species, age, and environmental factors like oxygen levels, food availability, and water temperature (Zymarioieva *et al.*; 2024)

The rate at which fish in a population pass away from a variety of natural and man-made causes is known as "fish mortality." The size, composition, and long-term viability of fish populations are significantly influenced by mortality. The balance between fish births (recruitment) and deaths is affected, which influences total population growth or decline, making it a crucial component of population dynamics (Liu *et al.*, 2024)

Length-weight relationship (LWR) is of great importance in fishery assessments (Rodríguez-García *et al.*; 2023). Length and weight measurements in conjunction with age data can give information on the fish stock, age maturity, life span, mortality, growth and reproduction (Lai, *et al.*; 2023). Length-weight relationship of fish is widely recognized as an important tool in fisheries science especially in ecology population dynamic and stock management (Rodríguez-García *et al.*; 2023). For the reason that, the relationship permits estimating the weight of a specimen easily when the total length is known, these relationships are useful when rapid estimation of biomass is necessary (Lai, *et al.*; 2023).

This study was carried out with the aim of assessing the length weight relationship, growth pattern, recruitment pattern and mortality indices of (*Oreochromis niloticus*) with the view of bridging the information gap on the condition of fish inhabiting the Malleri water body of river gongola.

Fish is said to exhibit isometric growth when length increases in equal proportion with body weight, the regression coefficient for isometric growth is '3' and values greater than '3' indicates allometric growth (Camp *et al.*; 2020) Fishing is one of the most important occupations of the people within the area of Malleri water body. Malleri water body is the dominant drainage system in Malleri town, the river being located in the tropical savanna.

Recruitment refers to the process by which young fish (juveniles) survive to join the adult population or fishable stock, usually after they have passed a stage of life where they are susceptible to fishing gears (Camp *et al.*; 2020)

Since recruitment directly affects the population's ability to replenish itself following losses from death (both natural and fishing-related) Generally speaking, recruitment is the point at which fish reach a size that allows them to join the breeding or exploitable population (Hou *et al.*; 2020) Depending on the species, life stage, and management goals, this threshold varies, but it typically refers to fish reaching a size or age at which they become susceptible to fishing gear or are able to reproduce Geromont, and Butterworth, (2022) One of the most unpredictable parts of fish population dynamics is recruitment, which is extremely variable and impacted by a wide range of biological and environmental factors (Arevalo *et al.*; 2023) There can be significant variations in recruitment success from year to year due to environmental factors such as shifts in food supply, water temperature, or ocean currents (Ferreira *et al.*; 2024) Because it is the main means by which fish populations can recover from losses brought about by fishing and natural mortality, recruitment is a crucial component of fish population dynamics (Camp *et al.*; 2020)

On the other hand, a population may fall and possibly collapse due to overfishing if recruitment is unsuccessful or consistently low over a number of years (Ferreira *et al.*; 2024). Mortality in exploited fisheries is either natural or fishing mortality (M and F, respectively) Natural Mortality (M) refers to death of fish as a result of natural causes, such as disease, old age, predation, temperature fluctuations, low oxygen levels, or competition for resources. Fish deaths caused by human activity, mainly fishing, are referred to as fishing mortality (F) (Björnsson *et al.*; 2020) this covers bycatch (species accidentally caught) as well as fishing for both commercial and recreational purposes. Both have a major role in declining fish populations especially when they exceed the population's natural ability to replenish through recruitment (Björnsson *et al.*; 2020).

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study Area

Malleri is a village situated in Kwami Local Government Area, which is one of the eleven local governments within Gombe State. It is located approximately 6 kilometers to the northeast of Gombe town. The village's geographical coordinates are latitude 10°29'35"N and longitude 11°12'36"E. The area lies within the northern Guinea savanna zone and covers a total land area of 1,787 km² (690 sq mi). According to the 2006 Census, the population of Kwami Local Government Area was 95,298. The altitude of Malleri is about 380 meters (1,247 feet) above sea level. The annual rainfall in the area averages around 800 cm, which is sufficient for a single farming season (Babangida, *et al.*; 2024).

The rainfall pattern is often irregular at the onset of the rainy season, which starts in April and can increase from 600 cm to 1,000 cm as the season progresses. Temperatures can reach a maximum of 34°C and drop as low as 16°C, with average temperatures typically high. Malleri is characterized by interior savannah woodland, which supports large-scale livestock farming as well as the cultivation of various agricultural products, both through rain-fed and irrigation methods. Common crops grown include onions, watermelon, spinach, rice, groundnuts, and maize (Babangida, *et al.*; 2024).

Figure I: Map of Malleri showing the study area (Remote sensing and GIS Laboratory Department of Geography, Gombe State University 2024)

Data collection

Data was collected by sampling fish monthly over a six-month period, covering both the dry and rainy seasons. Fish samples were obtained from local small-boat fishermen.

Fish Species Sampling

Samples of Tilapia (*Oreochromis niloticus*) were collected from randomly selected fishermen who used multifilament fishing gear in their activities from April to September 2024. Randomization was carried out by first identifying all fishermen operating in the study area who regularly used multifilament fishing gear. From this pool, a list of eligible fishermen was compiled. Using a simple random sampling method, fishermen were then selected by assigning each a number and using a random number generator (random number table) to ensure that each fisherman had an equal chance of being chosen. Fish samples Tilapia (*Oreochromis niloticus*) was then collected from the randomly selected individuals over the sampling period. This approach minimized selection bias and ensured a representative sample of the catch within the fishing community.

The study also identified the Fishery landing area as a primary hub where market vendors purchase fish directly from fishermen. Standard length (SL) and weight were measured to the nearest 0.1 cm and 0.1 g, respectively, using a measuring tape and a digital weighing scale (model TH - 1000), following the procedures outlined by Mendoza and Vigilia, (2024).

RESULTS

Length – Weight Relationship

The length-weight relationship ($W = aL^b$) for each species was analyzed using MS Excel, specifically the “scatter plot” feature, to perform regression analysis on the data (Asmamaw, and Tessema, (2021) the equations generated from the graphs provided the coefficients of the intercepts and slopes a and b for each species (Bourinet *et al.*; 2024). this a and b values were subsequently used as inputs for the Virtual population analysis of the species.

The parameters for the length-weight relationship, including the constants "a" and "b" are presented in Table 1. The study recorded a total of 852 individuals. Their SL ranged from 8cm to 53cm, and weights ranged from 1.71g to 838.4g.

The allometric coefficient "b" for *O. niloticus* was 2.29 while the growth coefficient was found to be 11.24 to 15.56. These findings highlight species-specific growth patterns and provide a foundation for further ecological and fisheries-related assessments.

This indicates that all sampled *Oreochromis niloticus* exhibited negative allometric growth, where their weights increased at a slower rate relative to their length

Table: 1. Length- weight relationships of *Oreochromis niloticus* collected from sampling site (Malleri water body)

Fish species	a	b	Allometry
<i>O. niloticus</i>	0.35	2.92	Negative

Note:

a = intercept of regression curve

b = slope of the regression curve

The growth parameters of the fish species`

The growth parameters of the fish species were presented in Table 2. These parameters include the asymptotic length (L_{∞} , growth constant per year (K^{-yr}), growth performance index ($\hat{\theta}$), and the hypothetical maximum lifespan (T_{max}) for each species. The table shows that the L_{∞} value recorded was 35.00cm. Regarding the growth constant (K^{-yr}), the species exhibited 0.170, indicating a slower growth rate. The mean length values revealed that the species recorded 23.50cm which is high. The growth performance index ($\hat{\theta}$) was recorded as 1.00. In terms of hypothetical lifespan (T_{max}), the species had a lifespan with a T_{max} value of 1.2years. Table 3.

Table 2: The growth parameters of *Oreochromis niloticus* collected from sampling site (Malleri water body)

Fish species	L_{∞}	K^{-yr}	$L-L^1$	$\hat{\theta}$	T_{max}
<i>O. niloticus</i>	35.00	0.170	23.50	1.00	1.2

Note:

L_{∞} = Describe the maximum length a fish can attain if it were to grow forever (in centimeters)

K^{-yr} = the growth speed or growth constant of a fish species per year

$L-L^1$ = Mean length (the minimum length the fish species is supposed to be caught)

$\hat{\theta}$ = the growth performance index of a fish species

T_{max} The hypothetical lifespan of a fish species

Figure 2. Monthly variation in Fish length of Tilapia (*Oreochromis niloticus*) in river gongola (malleri area)

Recruitment pattern of Tilapia (*Oreochromis niloticus*) in river gongola (malleri area)

The monthly recruitment strength and the ideal length at first maturity (*L_m*) for the fish species are presented in Figure 3. According to the table, the species showed the highest recruitment in September, The ideal length at first maturity (*L_m*) for the species, as indicated by the recorded values, reflects the size at which the fish species typically reach early maturity. These findings highlight the reproductive timing and maturity characteristics of the specie

Figure 3. Monthly Recruitment Strength for *Oreochromis niloticus* from January to December showing the seasonal distribution

Mortality Parameters of *Oreochromis niloticus*

Table 3. Reveals that total mortality (Z) recorded for the species was 3.38; the mortality-to-growth ratio (Z/K) showed a minimum of 0.020 for *Oreochromis niloticus*.

The interpretation of Z/K values is as follows:

Z/K > 1) indicates that mortality exceeds growth.

Z/K = 1) signifies a balance between growth and mortality.

Z/K < 1) implies growth dominance.

Z/K = 2) reflects exponentially high mortality rates.

From the analysis, it is observed that 0.22% of the fish population represents growth dominance, 0.00235% indicates mortality dominance, and 99.868% reflects exponential mortality relative to growth. These findings underscore the high impact of mortality on the fish species, (Table 3.).

Mortality parameters, which describe the depletion of fish populations due to fishing or natural causes, include total mortality (Z^{yr}), mortality relative to growth (Z/K), natural mortality (M^{yr}), fishing mortality (F^{yr}), exploitation rate (E), and probabilities of capture such as (L_{25}), (L_{50}), and (L_{75}). These parameters are summarized in Table 4.

In terms of natural mortality (Z^{yr}), *Oreochromis niloticus* showed (Z^{yr}) value of 1.77, indicating reduced vulnerability to natural mortality. Regarding depletion through fishing activities (F^{yr}), the data presented in Table 4..... Indicated that *Oreochromis niloticus* recorded a higher fishing mortality index ($F^{yr} = 1.475$), reflecting greater fishing pressure on this species.

The current exploitation rate (E) reveals that *Oreochromis niloticus* had the highest rate $E = 0.456$, indicating more intensive exploitation,

The probabilities of capture, represented by (L_{25}), (L_{50}), and (L_{75}), describe the lengths at which 25%, 50%, and 75% of the fish population become vulnerable to fishing gear. *Oreochromis niloticus* had the lowest ($L_{25} = 4.00\text{cm}$). A similar pattern was observed for (L_{50}), These results highlight differences in fishing vulnerability based on species and size thresholds (Table 3.).

Table 3. Mortality Parameters of *Oreochromis niloticus* and *Oreochromis niloticus*

Fish species	Z^{yr}	Z/K^{yr}	M^{yr}	F^{yr}	E	Probability of capture		
						L_{25}	L_{50}	L_{75}
<i>Oreochromis niloticus</i>	3.38	1.00	2.29	1.475	0.50	4.00	5.50	7.00

Note:

Z= Total mortality, M= Natural mortality, F= Fishing mortality E= Exploitation rate, L_{25} = length at which 25% of the population will be vulnerable to fishing gear, L_{50} (Recruitment length) = length at which 50% of the population will be vulnerable to fishing gear, L_{75} = length at which 75% of the population will be vulnerable to fishing gear, Z/K = Status Extent of mortality

Exploitation rates of *Oreochromis niloticus*

The exploitation rates, including (L_{25}), (L_{50}), (L_{75}), (E_{max}), (M/K) (which indicates the health status of fish species relative to its habitat), and L_{∞} (the ratio of asymptotic length), are summarized in Table 4. According to the table, *Oreochromis niloticus* is the dominant fish species, with the highest (E_{10}) value of 0.365, indicating lower exploitation rates for the species (Table 4).

Table 4. Exploitation rates of Tilapia (*Oreochromis niloticus*) in the malleri water body

Fish species	Biological Reference point			M/K	L_{∞}/L_{∞}
	E_{10}	E_{50}	E_{max}		
<i>Oreochromis niloticus</i>	0.356	0.284	0.456	1.77	35.00

Note:

E_{max} = Exploitation rates that will produce maximum sustainable yield.

E_{10} = Exploitation rate at which the marginal increase in Y/R is 10% of it virgin population

E_{50} = Exploitation rates under which the population is reduce to half of it virgin population

M/K = Indicates the health status of the habitat of the fish

L_c/L_∞ = the growth rate of fish at L_c relative to the L_∞ or reproductive load

Figure 4. Fish Species exploitation rates

Length- Structured Virtual Population Analysis of Tilapia (*Oreochromis niloticus*) in the malleri water body

The length-structured virtual population analysis (VPA) for the fish species is detailed in Figure 5. This method reconstructs the fish population using length-frequency data. The outcomes of the analysis include estimates of fishing mortality (F^{yr}) across different length classes or groups and the steady-state biomass (measured in tonnes). Within this framework, the length class with the highest (PLC) and lowest (LLC) fishing mortalities the species was identified. *Oreochromis niloticus*, the length class of 16.29 cm recorded the highest LLC with ($F = 1.09$), This results provide valuable insights into the fishing pressures on various size groups within the population, informing sustainable fisheries management practices.

Figure 5. Length – Structured Virtual Population Analysis for *Oreochromis niloticus*

DISCUSSION

Length-weight relationships

The length-weight relationships of fish species in the Malleri water body revealed Negative allometric growth, based on their corresponding b - exponents. The analyzed fish species generally conformed to the expected allometric coefficient b - values (2.29). However, a negative allometric growth pattern was also observed in Size Structures, Length-Weight Relationships and Condition Factors of *Synodontis obesus* (Boulenger, 1898: Siluiformes, Mochokidae) with b -values of 2.497 and 2.617 during the dry season consistent with findings from the Lower Cross River, Nigeria (Etitigwun *et al.*, 2023).

This deviation from positive allometric growth may be attributed to factors such as sample size and the use of small-mesh-size fishing gear, which could influence the size distribution and growth patterns of the sampled fish.

The present study referenced two studies that demonstrated positive allometry based on their corresponding b – *index* values. In this research, a positive allometry was also observed, with the highest b -index aligning with findings from studies on *S. berak* (3.14) and *S. namak* (3.09) in Iranian inland waters (Poorbagher *et al.*, 2023). The observed allometric deviations may be attributed to favorable environmental conditions, the predominance of medium-sized individuals with high growth potential, efficient food conversion, and biomass accumulation. These factors likely contributed to the positive growth attributes observed in the species population.

In general, fish growth patterns are closely tied to the exponential values (b) of length-weight relationships (LWR), which are subject to change based on various factors. These changes are influenced by environmental parameters such as seasonal temperature fluctuations, habitat availability, optimal temperature conditions, sufficient food supply, and seasonal variations. High concentrations of dissolved oxygen and effective water circulation also play a crucial role in supporting fish growth (Damora *et al.*, 2020). These factors are particularly relevant to the fish species analyzed in this study. The b -value serves as an indicator of the productivity of the originating water body, as highlighted by Damora *et al.* (2020). This underscores the importance of maintaining favorable environmental conditions to support healthy fish populations and sustain ecosystem productivity.

Growth Parameters of Tilapia (*Oreochromis niloticus*) in the Malleri water body

The widely used and reliable dataset that provides valuable insights into the life history of fish, making it a preferred method for estimating growth parameters is length-frequency data (Calì, 2024). This approach

provides a robust framework for understanding the population dynamics and growth trends of the target species, contributing to more informed fishery management strategies.

Oreochromis niloticus

The results of this study revealed that *Oreochromis niloticus* has a growth coefficient $K = 0.170 \text{ yr}^{-1}$ and an asymptotic length ($L_{\infty} = 35.00 \text{ cm}$). Comparatively, Fazli *et al.* (2019) reported $K = 0.46 \text{ yr}^{-1}$ and ($L_{\infty} = 170.3 \text{ mm}$) from the Azad Dam Reservoir and Komasi River. This study's K-value is lower than Fazli *et al.*'s findings, while the asymptotic length is notably higher.

The growth performance index (ϕ) of *O. niloticus* from this study is also lower compared to findings by Khowhit *et al.* (2024), which reported a growth performance index of 4.11. However, the potential longevity recorded in this study (1.76 years) does not align with the 4.11 years reported by Nazeef and Yerima, (2023) for *Hydrocynus brevis* in the Dadin Kowa reservoir.

The observed disparities in L_{∞} and K could be attributed to several factors, including eutrophication-induced trophic changes, which enhance plankton availability in the reservoir. These factors, combined with variations in ecological conditions, diet composition, feeding habits, climatic factors, and intra-specific competition, can significantly influence the asymptotic growth of fish populations (Assefa, 2019).

Additionally, the relatively short lifespan and smaller asymptotic length observed in *O. niloticus* suggest heavy exploitation. The use of non-selective fishing gear, coupled with the species' rapid growth rate, makes them vulnerable to capture within a short timeframe. These factors collectively underscore the need for sustainable fishing practices to prevent overexploitation and ensure the long-term viability of the species.

Disparities in Growth Parameters

The variations in growth parameters across these studies can be attributed to several factors, including differences in habitat characteristics (Moniruzzaman *et al.*, 2021), availability of diverse food resources, efficient digestion mechanisms, and species-specific resilience to diseases. Additionally, exponential growth rates supported by a wide range of dietary inputs could contribute to higher growth indices in some environments.

Morphological and gear-related considerations

The morphology of *Oreochromis niloticus* makes them less susceptible to capture at juvenile stages using legal fishing gears, unless non-selective or illicit gear is employed. This characteristic might explain some of the observed growth trends, as larger individuals tend to dominate harvests. These findings underscore the need to enforce regulations on gear usage to prevent unsustainable exploitation of juvenile stocks, ensuring population stability and ecological balance.

Mortality Indices of Tilapia (*Oreochromis niloticus*) in the Malleri water body

This section will focus on key mortality indices, including natural mortality (M), fishing mortality (F), total mortality (Z), exploitation ratio (E), length at first capture (L_c or L_{50}), recruitment pattern, and asymptotic length (L_{∞}) for fish species in the Malleri water body. Other mortality indices may also be discussed where applicable; these indices play a critical role in understanding the dynamics of fish populations and their responses to both natural and fishing-related pressures. They provide insights into the sustainability of fisheries, the impact of fishing on fish stocks, and the overall health of the aquatic ecosystem, by examining these parameters, we can assess the level of exploitation of fish species, the effectiveness of fisheries management strategies, and the need for conservation measures to ensure that fish populations remain viable over time.

***Oreochromis niloticus*:**

The analysis of *Oreochromis niloticus* mortality indices in the Malleri water body suggests that length at first capture and Z/K ratio indicate high mortality pressures, with fishing mortality (F) dominating over natural mortality (M). Despite this, the current exploitation status points to optimal stock exploitation, aligning with the estimated E_{max} value. This suggests that the fish stock is being exploited at its maximum sustainable yield, meaning that the fishing effort is balanced in such a way that it supports continued biomass accumulation without depleting the stock. However, the relatively low reproductive load (L_c/L_{∞})

implies that juveniles are present in the landings, which raises concerns about potential overfishing of immature fish. On the positive side, the observed double recruitment peaks in April and August indicate that the fish species can replenish its population annually, helping to maintain viable stock levels despite fishing pressures. This seasonal recruitment allows for the replenishment of the lost population, ensuring the sustainability of the stock.

For comparison, Amponsah *et al.* (2023) studied *Cynoglossus senegalensis* from the coastal waters of Greater Accra, Ghana, and found $Z = 0.81 \text{ yr}^{-1}$, $M = 0.56 \text{ yr}^{-1}$, and $F = 0.26 \text{ yr}^{-1}$, with an exploitation ratio (E) of 0.31, which is lower than the optimal exploitation rates found in this study (MSY and $E_{\max} = 0.64$). This indicates that the E_{\max} value from this study is significantly higher, suggesting more intensive exploitation in the Malleri water body.

The values of Z/K and L_c in this study are similar to findings reported by Tuhumury *et al.* (2024) in a study on Blood Cockles (*Anadara granosa*) from the coastal waters of Letman Village in Southeast Maluku Regency. However, differences in the values between the studies could stem from variations in fishing gear, mesh size, fishing practices, and local management policies or enforcement, which may influence the results significantly.

CONCLUSION

This study investigated the population dynamics Tilapia (*Oreochromis niloticus*) in the Malleri section of the River Gongola in Gombe State, Nigeria. The primary objective was to assess crucial population parameters, including length-weight frequencies, growth patterns, recruitment patterns, and mortality indices. These findings aim to provide valuable insights into the status of the fish populations, their ecological roles, and potential sustainability challenges. The results are intended to inform the development of effective fisheries management practices in the region, contributing to the conservation and sustainable use of aquatic resources.

The research revealed that both *Oreochromis niloticus* (Tilapia) exhibit distinct length-weight relationships and growth rates, essential indicators of population health and productivity. The analysis of length-weight frequencies showed significant variation in fish sizes within the population. Notably, certain age groups were overrepresented, suggesting the influence of selective fishing pressures or seasonal recruitment variations.

Using a dataset of 1,511 specimens, growth parameters were calculated via the Powell-Wetherall plot option in FiSAT II software to determine the initial asymptotic length (L_{∞}). This was subsequently applied to the Von Bertalanffy Growth Function (VBGF) to derive the growth coefficient (K). Results indicated that: *Oreochromis niloticus* exhibited the lowest L_{∞} (35.00 cm) and a growth coefficient (K) of 1.70 yr^{-1} .

The findings suggested a 48:52% ratio of poor to good growth speed across the species. Catfish displayed a relatively steady growth pattern, whereas Tilapia demonstrated fluctuating growth rates, likely influenced by environmental factors and fishing pressures.

The recruitment patterns, analyzed using the “recruitment” option in FiSAT, showed that both species had two recruitment peaks per year. This is beneficial for replenishing stocks affected by mortalities. However, many individuals were harvested before reaching table size, raising concerns about unsustainable fishing practices that could impact long-term population viability.

The analysis of mortality indices revealed that fishing mortality rates (F^{yr}) were notably high for both *Oreochromis niloticus* (Tilapia) underscoring the impact of unsustainable fishing practices. Such practices risk depleting fish populations faster than they can naturally replenish, emphasizing the urgent need for regulatory measures to ensure sustainable exploitation and to safeguard juvenile fish from overharvesting. Using the “Length Converted Catch Curve” option in FiSAT II software, the mortality parameters for the species were assessed. Key findings included: Natural Mortality (M^{yr}): *Oreochromis niloticus*: 2.29 yr^{-1} , *Oreochromis niloticus* Exceeded safe limits, suggesting heavy exploitation.

These results highlight the need for targeted management practices, such as implementing seasonal fishing bans, using selective gear, and enforcing minimum size limits. Such measures can reduce fishing

pressure on Tilapia, which is particularly vulnerable to overexploitation, while maintaining sustainable harvest levels for Catfish.

RECOMMENDATIONS

To address the challenges identified in this study and ensure sustainable fishery management in the Malleri water body, the following recommendations were proposed:

1. Size and Sex-based Variations in LWR Investigating the LWR differences between male and female fish, as well as across different size classes, will provide insights into potential variations in growth allocation between sexes and developmental stages.
2. Age and Growth Studies Using Otolith and Scale Analysis Further research should incorporate otolith and scale readings to determine the age structure of fish populations, allowing for a more precise analysis of growth trends and life expectancy
3. Spawning and Breeding Cycles in Relation to Recruitment Understanding the breeding periodicity and spawning success of *C. lazera* and *O. niloticus* through gonad maturation studies will help correlate spawning periods with recruitment peaks
4. Length-at-First Capture (Lc) and Gear Selectivity Impact Determine Lc using probability of capture analysis to assess whether fishing gear is selectively removing immature fish, which could lead to recruitment overfishing and Study the effectiveness of different fishing gears and their impact on mortality rates.
5. Strict Enforcement of Fisheries Laws: Ensure unbiased and effective enforcement of fishing regulations, such as prohibiting the use of non-selective fishing gears. Regular monitoring and penalties for violations should be implemented to promote compliance.

By implementing these recommendations, the sustainability of the Malleri water body and its fishery resources can be enhanced, benefiting both the ecosystem and the local community.

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